

Benzilic Acid Complexes of Niobium(V) and Tantalum(V)

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Reactions of pentaethoxides and pentachlorides of niobium and tantalum with benzilic acid have been carried out in different molar ratios and compounds of the type, $[M(OEt)_{5-2n}(Bz)_n]$ and $[MCl_{5-2n}(Bz)_n]$ (where Bz represents the benzilato group, $M=Nb$ or Ta and $n=1$ or 2) have been isolated. Alcoholysis reactions of $[M(OEt)_{5-2n}(Bz)_n]$ with excess of *tert*-butanol were also carried out and product of type, $[M(OBu^t)_{5-2n}(Bz)_n]$ were obtained. All the new complexes synthesised were characterised by elemental analysis, molecular weight determinations, ir and nmr spectral studies.

In earlier publication, we have reported the synthesis of some novel β -diketonates¹ of niobium and tantalum. Now, we report the synthesis of some benzilates of niobium and tantalum(V). Funk and coworkers² have reported that basic acetates are formed by the reaction of pentachlorides of niobium and tantalum with acetic acid. Pentaethoxides of niobium and tantalum react with lower and higher carboxylic acids in different stoichiometric ratios³.

(where $M=Nb$ or Ta and $n=1, 2$ or 3)

However, when the reactions were carried out in molar ratio $1:4$ or $1:>4$ the lower carboxylic acids gave the corresponding basic carboxylates and the higher carboxylic acids formed monoethoxide tetracarboxylates.

($R=CH_3, C_2H_5$ or C_3H_7)

($R=C_{11}H_{23}, C_{15}H_{31}$ or $C_{17}H_{35}$)

These derivatives are soluble in common organic solvents except the basic carboxylates which are insoluble.

Kapoor and coworkers⁴ have reported the reactions of pentaethoxides of niobium and tantalum with various hydroxy carboxylic acids e.g., lactic, mandelic or salicylic acids :

Recently we have studied the reactions of isopropoxides and chlorides of aluminium, titanium, and zirconium with benzilic acid and interesting results were obtained⁵. A survey of literature reveals that no such work has been done with niobium and tantalum.

In view of the above, it was considered worthwhile to study the reactions of ethoxides and chlorides of niobium and tantalum with benzilic acid in different molar ratios in refluxing benzene :

(where $M=Nb$ or Ta , H_2Bz =Benzilic acid)

The completion of reaction was checked by estimating the liberated ethanol azeotropically⁶ in case of ethoxides and $HCl(gas)$ in case of chloride reactions.

In both the reactions, it was found that reaction proceeds with the removal of only four moles of ethanol or chlorine even when excess of benzilic acid was used. It has been observed that removal of the fifth mole of ethoxy as well as chloride is very difficult even when an excess of the ligand was taken and refluxing time was increased. This may be attributed to steric hindrance of the bulky benzilic acid or saturated coordination state of metal in disubstituted derivatives.

The complexes isolated are highly soluble in organic solvents in the case of ethoxide derivatives

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while the chloride derivatives are partially soluble in CHCl_3 , CCl_4 and benzene. These chloro complexes are soluble in dimethyl formamide and dimethyl sulphoxide. Attempts were also made to sublime them under reduced pressure, but they tend to decompose at $\sim 120\text{-}160^\circ/0.02$ mm.

The nmr spectra of the compounds (Table 1) $[\text{M}(\text{OEt})_{5-2n}(\text{Bz})_n]$ (where $\text{M}=\text{Nb}$ or Ta and $n=1$ or 2) in CDCl_3 show CH_3 protons and $-\text{CH}_2$ protons of ethoxy group in the region 1.1-1.3 ppm as triplet and 3.5-3.9 ppm as quadruplet respectively⁷ (Table 1). The multiplet in the region 6.9-7.2 ppm clearly indicate the presence of phenyl ring⁷. The chloro substituted benzilato derivatives show a multiplet in the region 7.1-7.4 ppm which may be assigned to the protons of phenyl group.

The infrared spectra of mono and *bis* benzilato derivatives of Nb(V) and Ta(V) show no absorption

TABLE 1 - CHARACTERISTICS INFRARED AND NMR DATA FOR BENZILATE COMPLEXES OF NIOBIUM AND TANTALUM

Sl. No.	Complex	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$-\text{CH}_3$ of ethoxy	$-\text{CH}_2$ of ethoxy	$-\text{phenyl ring}$
		ir data		nmr data	(ppm) in δ	
1.	$[\text{Nb}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{Bz})]$	1630 s	550 s	1.1-1.3 (t)	3.5-3.7 (q)	7.0-7.2 (m)
2.	$[\text{Nb}(\text{OEt})(\text{Bz})_2]$	1630 s	560 s	1.2-1.4 (t)	3.5-3.7 (q)	7.0-7.2 (m)
3.	$[\text{Ta}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{Bz})]$	1625 s	535 sb	1.1-1.3 (t)	3.4-3.7 (q)	7.1-7.4 (m)
4.	$[\text{Ta}(\text{OEt})(\text{Bz})_2]$	1640 sb	555 sb	1.1-1.3 (t)	3.3-3.5 (q)	7.2-7.4 (m)
5.	$[\text{NbCl}_5(\text{Bz})]$	1660 s	550 m	-	-	6.9-7.2 (m)
6.	$[\text{NbCl}_3(\text{Bz})_2]$	1610 s	550 m	-	-	6.9-7.1 (m)
7.	$[\text{TaCl}_5(\text{Bz})]$	1680 s	550 mb	-	-	7.0-7.2 (m)
8.	$[\text{TaCl}_3(\text{Bz})_2]$	1670 s	550 mb	-	-	6.9-7.3 (m)

band in the $\sim 3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region indicating the absence of hydroxy groups (alcoholic as well as carboxylic) of benzoic acid.

The asymmetric carbonyl stretching frequency which appeared at 1740 cm^{-1} as a strong band in benzoic acid has been shifted to lower frequency ($60\text{-}80 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicating the coordination of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group to the metal. The strong band at $\sim 535\text{-}560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ while $\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})$ absorbed at $\sim 390 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The other characteristic bands are assigned in Table 3.

The molecular weight of soluble complexes in refluxing benzene were determined and found that these complexes are of dimeric nature.

On the basis of above studies and elemental analysis, the following seven and eight coordinated structures can tentatively be assigned to compounds of the type $[\text{M}(\text{OEt})_{5-2n}(\text{Bz})_n]$ (where $\text{M}=\text{Nb}$ or Ta and $n=1$ or 2) respectively.

It appears that in *bis* derivatives of niobium or tantalum, the metal atoms are so well shielded in dimeric structure that further coordination of reacting benzoic acid molecule becomes sterically hindered. Due to this, further reaction do not take place even with excess of ligand with prolonged refluxing.

Due to partially soluble nature of chloro complexes in benzene it was not possible to determine their molecular weight.

Alcoholysis reactions of the compounds $[\text{M}(\text{OEt})_{5-2n}(\text{Bz})_n]$ were also carried out with excess of *tert*-butanol and compounds having general formula, $[\text{M}(\text{OBu}^t)_{5-2n}(\text{Bz})_n]$ where $\text{M}=\text{Nb}$ or Ta , and $n=1$ or 2 , were isolated and characterised (Table 2). The liberated ethanol was estimated by oxidimetric method⁹.

Experimental

All glass apparatus with standard quickfit joints were used throughout the experimental work. Stringent precautions were taken to exclude moisture.

Benzene (AR,BDH), ethanol, *tert*-butanol (SD) were dried and purified by standard methods. NbCl_5 (Fluka), TaCl_5 (Riedel), benzoic acid AnalaR

TABLE 2—INTERCHANGE REACTIONS OF $[M(OEt)_{5-2n}(L)_n]$ WITH *tert*-BUTANOL
 (where M = Nb or Ta and n = 1 or 2, L = Benzilic acid)

Sl. No.	Reactants		Refluxing time (hr)	Product formed, state and decomposition temp.	Analysis	
	Complex taken (g) (mole)	Wt. of <i>tert</i> -butanol taken (g)			Metal (%) Found (Calcd.)	Amount of ethanol in azeotrope (g) Found (Calcd.)
1.	Nb(OEt) ₅ (Bz) 0.19 (0.0004)	excess	7	Nb(OBu ^t) ₃ (Bz) Light yellow, solid 165	17.9 (17.2)	0.06 (0.06)
2.	Nb(OEt)(Bz) ₂ 0.40 (0.0007)	excess	6	[Nb(OBu ^t)(Bz) ₂] Light yellow, solid 150	16.0 (15.9)	0.03 (0.03)
3.	Ta(OEt) ₅ (Bz) 0.39 (0.0007)	excess	8	[Ta(OBu ^t) ₃ (Bz)] Light yellow, solid 210	28.3 (28.9)	0.10 (0.10)
4.	Ta(OEt)(Bz) ₂ 0.56 (0.0008)	excess	6	[Ta(OBu ^t)(Bz) ₂] Light yellow, solid 180	25.4 (25.6)	0.04 (0.04)

grade (E. Merck) were used as supplied. Niobium and tantalum pentaethoxides were prepared by standard methods^{8,9,10}.

Molecular weights were determined in benzene with the help of semimicro ebulliometer (Gallenkamp) using thermistor sensing. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer-621 spectrophotometer using nujol mulls, cesium iodide pellets or KBr pellets. The nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on Perkin Elmer R-32 spectrometer. Ethanol was estimated by oxidimetric method⁶ using $NK_2Cr_2O_7$ in 12.5% sulphuric acid. Niobium and tantalum were estimated as Nb₂O₅ and Ta₂O₅ by direct ignition of compounds after digestion with ammonia and nitric acid in platinum crucible. C, H were determined by micro analytical laboratory of Chemistry Department, Delhi University, Delhi.

Reactions :

(i) *Reaction of niobium pentaethoxide and benzilic acid (molar ratio 1 : 1)* : To a solution of Nb(OEt)₅ (0.46 g ; 0.0014 M) in benzene was added benzilic acid (0.33 g ; 0.0014M). A suspension appeared at the time of addition which became clear after refluxing for 6 hr. The ethanol liberated during the reaction was collected azeotropically and estimated⁶. The excess of solvent was distilled off and final product was dried under vacuum at 40°/0.5 mm ; a light yellow solid was obtained.

Found : Ethanol in azeotrope, 0.13 g ; Nb, 20.46 %. Calcd. for [Nb(OEt)₃(Bz)] : ethanol in azeotrope, 0.13 g ; Nb, 20.7 %.

For the sake of brevity other reactions are given in Table 3a.

TABLE 3a—REACTIONS OF NIOBIUM AND TANTALUM PENTA ETHOXIDES WITH BENZILIC ACID

Sl. No.	Molar ratio	Alkoxide g (mole)	Benzilic acid g (mole)	Refluxing time (hr)	Product, state, yield (%) and decomposition temp (°C)	Amount of alcohol in azeotrope (g) : Found (Calcd.)	Analysis :			Mol. wt. in benzene : Found (Calcd.)
							Metal % Found (Calcd.)	C % Found (Calcd.)	H % Found (Calcd.)	
1.	1 : 1	0.46 (0.0014)	0.33 (0.0014)	6	[Nb(OEt) ₃ (Bz)] Light yellow, solid (80) 180	0.13 (0.13)	20.7 (20.4)	52.5 (53.0)	4.2 (5.5)	895.3 (454.3)
2.	1 : 2	0.44 (0.0013)	0.63 (0.0027)	8	[Nb(OEt)(Bz) ₂] Light yellow, solid (80) 173	0.23 (0.25)	16.2 (15.7)	—	—	1200.0 (590.4)
3.	1 : 1	0.93 (0.0023)	0.52 (0.0023)	7	[Ta(OEt) ₃ (Bz)] Light yellow, solid (85) 192	0.21 (0.21)	33.4 (33.3)	45.7 (44.4)	3.9 (4.4)	1096.8 (542.3)
4.	1 : 2	0.76 (0.0018)	0.85 (0.0037)	10	[Ta(OEt)(Bz) ₂] Light yellow, solid (88) 199	0.35 (0.35)	26.5 (26.7)	51.9 (53.2)	2.9 (3.7)	1219.0 (678.4)

TABLE 3(b) - REACTIONS OF NIOBIUM AND TANTALUM PENTA CHLORIDES WITH BENZILIC ACID

Sl. No.	Molar ratio	Metal chloride g (mole)	Benzilic acid (g) (mole)	Refluxing time (hr)	Product, state yield (%) and decomposition temp (°C)	Metal (%) Found (Calcd.)	Chlorine (%) Found (Calcd.)	C (%) Found (Calcd.)	H (%) Found (Calcd.)
1.	1 : 1	1.82 (0.0067)	1.54 (0.0067)	36	[NbCl ₅ (Bz)] Light brown, solid (80) 195	22.1 (21.8)	24.5 (24.9)	39.2 (39.6)	2.5 (2.4)
2.	1 : 2	1.03 (0.0038)	1.75 (0.0076)	50	[NbCl(Bz) ₂] Light brown, solid (78) 190	16.4 (15.9)	6.0 (6.1)	56.1 (58.0)	4.6 (3.5)
3.	1 : 1	1.01 (0.0028)	0.64 (0.0028)	40	[TaCl ₅ (Bz)] Light brown, solid (80) 140	35.0 (35.2)	20.5 (20.7)	31.4 (32.8)	2.4 (1.9)
4.	1 : 2	0.87 (0.0024)	1.10 (0.0048)	60	[TaCl(Bz) ₂] Light brown, solid (80) 140	26.8 (27.0)	5.6 (5.2)		

(ii) *Reaction between tris ethoxy niobium(V) benzilate and excess of tert-butanol*: To a solution of [Nb(OEt)₃(Bz)] (0.19 g; 0.0004 M) in benzene was added excess of *tert*-butanol (~5 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 7 hr. The ethanol so liberated was collected azeotropically and estimated⁶. The excess of solvent was distilled off and the final product was dried under *vacuo* at 40°/0.5 mm; a light yellow solid was obtained.

Found: Ethanol in azeotrope, 0.05 g; Nb, 18.2%. Calcd. for [Nb(OBu^t)₃(Bz)]: ethanol in azeotrope 0.05 g; Nb, 17.9%.

The details of other reactions are given in Table 2.

(iii) *Reaction between niobium pentachloride and benzilic acid(H₂Bz) (molar ratio 1:1)*: Benzilic acid (1.54 g; 0.0067M) was added to a suspension of niobium pentachloride (1.82 g; 0.0067M) in benzene. An exothermic reaction started with evolution of hydrogen chloride gas. The mixture was refluxed in an oil bath at 110° for about 36 hr and checked continuously. When no more hydrogen chloride gas evolved, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure leaving behind a light brown solid mass.

Found: Nb, 21.8%; Cl, 24.5%. Calcd. for NbCl₅(Bz); Nb, 22.1%; Cl, 24.9%.

The other reactions are given in Table 3b.

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